

**IMPACT OF CORONAVIRUS PANDEMIC ON THE INDIAN EDUCATION SECTOR: A
PERSPECTIVES OF TEACHERS ON ONLINE TEACHING & ASSESSMENT**

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Introduction:

COVID-19, an infectious virus, spread all over the world and adversely affected all facets of the economy. This economic earthquake reached into an astonishing array of many sectors, mutilating them to a great extent. It is estimated that the impact of COVID-19 on the Indian economy during 2020 may reach nearly 8.8tn Indian rupees. The pandemic had incurred an enormous loss to the economy and had a staggering impact on global education. According to UNESCO, 63 million teachers were affected in 165 countries. The Director of the Division of Policies and Lifelong Learning Systems also highlighted the concern that prolonged closure of schools may have major implications on teaching, learning, assessments and credentials. The disruption of teaching and examination has delayed student progression and resulted in a broader socio-economic impact.

In India, the government has proclaimed the internment and closure of educational institutions as a logical resolution to enforce social distancing among communities. To support their call Ministry of Human Resource Development in their release (March twenty one, 2020) shared varied free digital e-learning platforms like the National Programs on Technology increased Learning, Respecting the decision of the government, many higher education institutions (HEIs) started to put their efforts to use technology in support of remote learning, distance education and online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic. It is pertinent that on-line teaching cannot be triple-crown while not the involvement of academics, as they're the frontline employees of any institution. COVID-19 epidemic has created it obligatory for the academics of developing countries to use on-line platforms for teaching and assessment to support the education sector. The academics have to be compelled to adapt the technology for the triple-crown execution of on-line teaching and assessments.

In India, on-line teaching isn't extremely popular. Most of the lecturers weren't well trained to show and conduct assessments on-line. As a result of internment, with no alternative, lecturers began to teach and conduct assessments from their homes.

Online teaching and assessment at home environment setting has different challenges from online teaching and conducting assessment in the university environment. The university environment has a conducive environment where all the facilities are available at ease. This research aims to identify those barriers that

are faced by the teachers during online teaching and assessment in the home environment setting in the Indian context. The findings of the study can be helpful to the regulatory authorities and employers of HEIs who are planning to adopt online teaching and assessment as a regular activity in the future.

➤ **Methodology**

Methodology Interpretative phenomenological analysis (IPA) of qualitative analysis methodology has been employed in this analysis. IPA aims to explore and perceive very well regarding the person's expertise of a selected development. During this analysis, IPA is employed to grasp the barriers moon-faced in on-line teaching and assessments throughout the age of COVID-19 wherever imprisonment had created lecturers teach and conduct the assessment in their home atmosphere settings.

➤ **Discussion**

Discussion while teaching within the home atmosphere setting, lecturers encountered several issues. The essential amenities for effective teaching and assessment need a whiteboard, marker and printer. Teaching and assessment need discipline and commitment however several parts indigenous elements like noise, visitors, music, family interference and social unit work existed in home atmosphere settings that adversely compact the standard of teaching and assessments.

➤ **Practical implications**

Sensible implications The findings of the study may be useful to the regulative authorities and employers of HEIs World Health Organization ar reaching to adopt on-line teaching and assessment as an everyday activity within the close to future. The known barriers may be thought-about before and a roadmap may be designed for swish execution of on-line teaching and assessment. as an example, within the release (29 Apr 2020) by the Ministry of Human Resource Development, in sight of COVID-19 and resulting imprisonment, University Grants Commission issued pointers on examinations and educational calendar (MHRD, 2020b). The insights gained on the barriers long-faced by the teacher throughout an internet assessment may be thought-about by HEIs to set up their examination consistently. Once the HEIs get back to the new normal, teachers can be trained to deal with these barriers for the smooth execution of online teaching and assessment.

➤ **Suggestion**

Every dark cloud comes with a silver lining, the lockdown has disturbed the education sector but HEIs have an option to start a new curriculum by integrating traditional and online learning. India should establish a good infrastructure for online education following some of the advanced countries. All higher education institutes now are aware of the importance of technology and should take serious measures to conduct technology-driven education through the LMS. This study offers the following suggestion:

➤ **Higher education institutions' planning**

Educational activity institutions' designing the education sector in Republic of India ought to understand the importance of technology and take up tight measures to implement the technology-driven teaching

sessions and assessment. HEI has to revise its existing policy frameworks by coming up with new ways and technical structures to help their academics for with success hold the Etch for coping with any crisis within the future. This study advocates that HEIs ought to use technology altogether aspects, starting with group action, delivery, assignments, examinations, devices, software, net property and power back-up, evaluations and results.

➤ **Teachers: self-development**

It is evident that the partnership between technology and education goes to remain forever. Supported this study, the academics are able to determine the issues they're going to face whereas conducting on-line categories and assessments. They're going to be able to equip themselves higher and might methods their efforts by enrolling in those courses which give coaching for conducting on-line teaching and assessment. Academics ought to often update their technical data. HEIs may also support their academics by providing coaching associated with technology and education and providing funds for enrolling in courses that target on-line teaching views.

➤ **Government support**

Non-availability of technical infrastructure and irregular interrupted net property all across Asian nation is that the biggest challenge before of the HEIs and academics. A collaboration of state, technology firms and better education institutes within the mode of public, personal firms, educational activity institutes partnership will solve the matter of technical infrastructure. Investment in institutional-supported technologies could be a pricey venture for HEIs, Government support can cut back the burden on the establishment and encourage them to adopt technology on-line teaching and assessments

➤ **Promoting sustainable development**

Promoting sustainable development HEIs will divide the courses into typical teaching and on-line teaching, it'll facilitate in inculcating the technology into the lecture rooms. The event of course-specific on-line teaching and assessment plans could be an entree for the strategic execution of technology within the room.

On-line teaching and assessment can cut back paper usage and can contribute to environmental property; it'll increase digital acquisition among academics and students which can increase their exposure and learning and creating them additional employable for the digital world-leading thereby conducive to social sustainability. Of these efforts can contribute to economic property by reducing state and conducive to economic process and development. Of these activities will facilitate in achieving the property development goals of Bharat.

Conclusion

COVID-19 pandemic has ushered the education system into a tech-savvy path. Though it is evident that online classes and assessments cannot substitute conventional mode of teaching but the role of technology and its extensive use in imparting education cannot be neglected.

The paper clearly projects the importance of institutional support technologies in online teaching and assessment. To imbibe technology-driven teaching in real or virtual, it is required to have an exclusive department devoted to developing the technological infrastructure of the institution. Training teachers in LMSs and making it mandatory for all educational purposes will put the institute, teachers and students in a separate league.

The future of education seems to be technology-driven and India has to equip itself for it, the paper identifies the huge gap that exists between the open-source versus institutional-supported technologies and its implication in online teaching and assessments.

The Ministry of Human Resources and Development, Government of India has recently proposed a draft on National Education Policy (NEP)-2020 where the focus is made on enhancing teaching and learning through online mode.

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